

President Rodrigo Duterte's Policies in Dealing With conflicts In Southern Philippines

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ABSTRACT : *This article aim to analyze and describe how President Rodrigo Duterte's Policies in dealing with conflicts in Southern Philippines. The Philippine government has made efforts in dealing conflict that occur in Mindanao, Southern Philippines. The conflict has a long historical background, so it needs the right approach to handle it and to realize positive peace. This article uses a qualitative approach with a literature review design related to efforts to achieve positive peace during Duterte's Presidential term. Data was collecting by compiling sources from various kinds of literature such as reading books, websites, and discussing with experts and competent groups in various efforts to achieve positive peace. The results showed that mediation and reconciliation efforts were carried out on an ongoing basis to resolve conflicts completely. However, there are obstacles and challenges in implementing the program. In conclusion, achieving positive peace in the Southern Philippines is still in progress. President Duterte's first step towards peace with the presence of the Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL) until the existence of BTA became the starting point for the realization of equity and social justice for all Filipinos.*

KEYWORDS -Duterte's Policies, Conflict, Peace, Bangsamoro, Southern Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is an archipelago state in Southeast Asia located in the western Pacific Rim. The Philippines was ruled by the Spanish Empire for 265 years starting from 1565 to 1821. However, in the American war against Spain in 1898, the US succeeded in controlling the Philippines and made it one of the commonwealth countries under the United States in 1934. During the Second World War, The Philippines was also occupied by Japan. The Philippines gained its independence from the United States on July 4, 1946 with the name of the country being the Republic of the Philippines (Republic of the Philippines) and the capital city of the Philippines is Manila. The Southern Philippines, better known as Mindanao, is located in the northern part of the islands of Sulawesi and Kalimantan. Mindanao is considered strategic because it is located between three countries, namely Indonesia, the Philippines, and Malaysia. The consequence of this position is that Mindanao is a trade route and goods traffic that connects the three countries (Surwandono, 2013).

The strategic position of the Southern Philippines, especially Mindanao, often experiences prolonged conflicts. The conflict in the Southern Philippines has been going on since the colonial era. The religious issues underlying this conflict made the situation even more heated. After the independence of the Philippines in 1946, the population of Mindanao, who are mostly Moro Muslims, still experiences discrimination and marginalization by the Philippine government, such as poverty, difficulty in obtaining employment, low levels of education, and even military violence (Surwandono, 2013). The Philippines also faces the problem of unequal economic distribution and separatist movements in the Mindanao region. Mindanao is the second-largest island in the south of the Philippines. Compared to other regions in the Philippines, Mindanao is an economically disadvantaged region with a high poverty rate.

Based on the data from the Family Income and Expenditure Survey (FIES) released by the Philippine Statistical Authority (PSA) in 2015, four of the five poorest areas in the Philippines are in Mindanao. Regions IX (Zamboanga Peninsula), Regions X (Northern Mindanao), Regions XII (Soccsksargen), Regions XIII (Caraga), and the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) were the regions with poverty rates above 39% in 2015. Meanwhile, the poverty rate in Regions XI (Davao) reached 26.7%; in other words, the poverty rate in these areas in 2015 was above the national average of 26.3%. Furthermore, ARMM is the poorest region with 59% of its 3.781.387 population living below the poverty line. Based on 2015 data, eight of the ten poorest provinces in the Philippines are located in Mindanao. At least since 2006, Mindanao Province has had the highest poverty rate (Gavilan, 2017).

The Philippines is one of the countries with the fastest economic growth rates in Southeast Asia. The Philippines' gross domestic product (GDP) increased by 6.4% in the 2010–2017 period, compared to the average growth in the 2000–2009 period which only reached 4.5% (Bird, 2022). So far, the Philippine economy has also depended on remittances, namely money sent by foreign workers to recipients in their home countries. This remittance is one of the largest cash flows in developing countries. This means that many Filipinos work abroad and invest in their country. In addition, the Philippine economy is also dependent on the global economy. The Philippines' economic growth declined by 3.6% in the first quarter of 2011, which was less than the growth target set by the Philippine Development Plan (PDP), which was 7%–8%. The decline was probably caused by the global economic crisis; and when compared to its neighboring countries, the Philippines' economy is in decline. Although remittances from Filipino migrant workers increased in early 2011, the compensation received by these migrant workers declined.

Mindanao's economic condition, which is more backward than the rest of the Philippines, has persisted for a long time. The Philippine government, particularly under President Fidel Ramos, has sought to reduce economic disparities in the region. One of the efforts made is by initiating subregional economic cooperation with ASEAN member countries in a forum called Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippine East ASEAN Growth Area (BIMP-EAGA). BIMP-EAGA which was established on March 26, 1994 in Davao City, Philippines, is the first step for the Philippines to accelerate economic growth in Mindanao, particularly in the areas of trade and investment.

In the historical development of their country, each president of the Philippines has a strategy related to the development of the economic welfare of the Filipino people. In an effort to develop the economic welfare of the Mindanao region, President Rodrigo Duterte who replaced Noynoy in 2016 issued Executive Order (EO) No. 5 as the legitimacy of “Ambisyon Natin 2040,” namely a long-term vision or 25-year development plan. This 25-year vision proclaims the Philippines to be a “prosperous country dominated by the middle class and no poor people.” Furthermore, this vision urges the Filipino people to live a healthy and long life, be smart and innovative, and live in a society that can be trusted. In this long-term vision, the government triples people's incomes and eliminates poverty and hunger by 2040, or sooner. In mid-2016, the Social Weather Stations survey showed that 46% of Filipinos were in the poor category. This figure is equivalent to 10.5 million Filipino families living in poverty. Poverty rates in several provinces have decreased slightly, except for Mindanao, Duterte's hometown (Duterte's Ambisyon Natin 2040: Middle-Class Society for PH, 2016).

The inequality in socio-economic and the impact of the prolonged conflict in Mindanao then prompted the community to establish a Moro Liberation Front (MLF) organization which later split into the Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF) and the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF). Their goal is Moro independence. The armed group carried out attacks on Philippine military forces as a form of protest against the rights they had not yet been granted (Tandio et al., 2016).

The process of resolving conflicts between the government and the Mindanao people in the Southern Philippines has been carried out several times by involving both parties, even a third party as a mediator. The protracted conflict creates conditions in which the security level is very low and economic instability. Finally, on September 2, 1996, a Final Peace Agreement was agreed between the government and the people of Mindanao to end the conflict (Christoffersen, 2002). Then, a historic moment occurred on Friday, January 25, 2019, where the Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL) of the Philippines, was officially passed after a referendum granting complete autonomy to Moro Muslims. More than 1.54 million people voted "Yes" to approve the BOL, while 190,000 voted against the law. The approval of the BOL means the Autonomous Region in Muslim

Mindanao (ARMM) in the Southern Philippines will be replaced with the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). The second phase of BOL will be held on February 6. Six small towns in Lanao del Norte and 39 villages in six districts of Cotabato Province and surrounding areas will vote in their participation in the autonomous region.

The discussion of this research will be focused on the term of president Duterte, because the BOL Act was the initiation of Rodrigo Duterte himself, where this law was designed to give Muslims overall autonomy, as well as judicial and economic advancement. Under the law, courts of Islamic Law will be opened in the region, and the Philippine Central Government will hand over its administrative authority in Mindanao to the Bangsamoro Government. The waters in the Bangsamoro Territory will be jointly managed by the National Government and the Bangsamoro Government. The Autonomous Government will be responsible for managing energy resources. In addition, former fighters from the Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF) and the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) will be able to join official forces (the Bangsamoro Law Passed After the Philippine Popular Consultation, 2019).

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Conflict Theory

Conflict comes from the Latin, namely "conflictus" which means conflict. This contradiction cannot be avoided because it is an intrinsic aspect of social change. Conflict is an expression of differences in interests, values, and beliefs that arise as new formations and are caused by social changes that appear contrary to inherited barriers (Hugh, 2002). The similarities and differences in social interests (perceived of interest) are the driving factors for conflict and integration. Therefore, conflict and integration are two things that cannot be avoided and will always decorate people's social life (Utoyo, 2016).

Social integration is the process of adjusting the different elements in people's lives so as to produce patterns of community life that have harmonious functions. Meanwhile, conflict is defined as a perception of different interests or a belief that the aspirations of the conflicting parties cannot be achieved simultaneously (simultaneously). Basically, the same perception and interest will not always happen. Therefore, differences in perceptions and interests will often be encountered in social life. This conflict or difference does not always lead to a negative, there is also a conflict that produces positive things. Because conflict is a form of interaction and there is no need to deny its existence. Because after all, inter-group and intra-group conflicts will always exist where people live together (Wirawan, 2013).

Therefore, conflict situations are divided into two, namely; realistic conflict and unrealistic conflict (Coser, 1956). Realistic conflict is a conflict that comes from the disappointment of individuals or community groups against the system and the demands that exist in social relations. Meanwhile, non-realistic conflict is a conflict that does not originate from the opposite goal of competition, but is a need for certain parties to relieve tension. Examples of non-realistic conflicts are looking for scapegoats for the problems that occur, so that the two conflicting parties can reduce tension, because the blame is transferred to a third party. In this case, the conflict in Mindanao is a realistic conflict.

2.2 Theory SAT (Structural, Accelerator, Trigger)

SAT can be interpreted as an objective fact that can influence the dynamics of conflict escalation. The first element is "S" which means "Structural", where this element can be likened to dry grass in a conflict (root causes of conflict), namely the main source of conflict or background that creates pre-conditions of social conflict. Usually, the main sources of these conflicts are structural and latent, such as poverty, inherent economic inequality, injustice, lack of adequate and responsive institutions, ecological damage to the region, and so on. These indicators are used to assess the risk of conflict in terms of potential conflicts that occurred during the previous decades (Malik, 2017).

Accelerator (A) is likened to the wind, where this accelerator is the cause of widespread conflict. Items included in accelerators are usually events outside the model parameters. In general, these A's are feedback events that can quickly increase the level of significance of the most violent common situations. Accelerators can be interpreted as a catalyst in the process of conflict escalation. Thus, an accelerator can be defined as a series of events or events that are not directly related to conflict indicators, but can trigger conflict escalation or

de-escalation very quickly. Various examples of accelerators are: government policies that are considered discriminatory against one particular group, armed conflict between two groups, increasing external support for one group, and increasing forms of violations of the integrity of human life.

The last element, namely Trigger, is likened to fire, namely the trigger for conflict which is usually a situational incident that causes conflicts that were initially latent to begin to surface and have the potential to reach the peak. Examples of this "T" factor are usually fights between two people from different ethnic groups or groups, the murder of important figures, electoral fraud, and political scandals. These things are usually only short term but can trigger people's emotions so that it leads to an escalation to the peak of the conflict.

Each factor, such as structural, accelerator, and trigger has specific characteristics. Structural (S) is a factor that has a long-term nature and is an ordinal indicator (can be measured up and down). While the trigger (T) has a short-term and sporadic nature. While the accelerator (A) is situational in nature which has an empirical and or logical relationship with the ups and downs of the S and T indicators.

This SAT framework must be implemented in a very thorough and structured manner. The principle used in formulating the SAT is to pay attention to a series of conflict events as something that flows and is chronological. SAT analysis should not be carried out discontinuously or eliminate the historical series of conflict events in the past. Because if this is done, there will be no common ground connecting the conflict factors and the conflict will become something that is difficult to solve. By implementing this SAT framework correctly, it is hoped that a conflict can be mapped easily so that positive peace in peace building can be realized correctly. (ITP, 2012).

III. DISCUSSION

3.1 The Dynamics of Conflict in the Southern Philippines During the Administration of President Rodrigo Duterte

The conflict in the Southern Philippines, more precisely in the Mindanao area, is a conflict that has a long and rooted history even since the colonial period in the Philippines in the 14th century. Since after the independence of the Philippines from colonial hands, the Philippines continued America's colonial policy by using the slogans of Filipinization and Christianization, this created tension and anxiety for Muslims in the Southern Philippines (Herbert, 2019). Even history explains that there had been a war between the Filipino people in the name of a holy mission, the war occurred between Muslims and Christians. The war occurred because of the politics of divide and rule (division and power) and mission-scare (holy mission of Christianization) which was initiated by the Spanish colonialists by targeting Muslims in Mindanao.

Mindanao Island is located in the southern Philippines, this area is an area with a majority Muslim population or known as Bangsamoro, and has a poor social situation. This is because sentiment towards the Muslim community living in this region has occurred since the beginning, there have been issues of economic, political injustice and the poor treatment of the Philippine government towards the Bangsamoro in Mindanao, so that this underlies the conflict between the Philippine government and the Bangsamoro.

Since the past, there has been discriminatory treatment by the Philippine Government against the Bangsamoro, making Muslims in this region establish a political organization that aims as a separatist movement to separate themselves from the Philippines. various groups include: Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), Moro Independent Movement (MIM), Bangsamoro Liberation Organization (BMLO), Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF), Islamic Command Council (ICC), to the terrorist group Abu Sayyaf (Bacani, 2005). Until now the conflict in the Mindanao region is still ongoing, even though the conflict has escalated, but the tension between the Philippine government and the Bangsamoro, especially the MILF group, has not yet come to light, because this area is still treated as a 'stepchild' who is not given enough attention to welfare development by the Philippine government.

As a democratic country, the Philippines is trying to keep the Mindanao region from being separated from its country. So then this requires the Philippine government to formulate the right policy, so that the existing separatist groups want to soften their hearts to remain incorporated as a unitary state of the Philippines. During the reign of President Rodrigo Duterte, the conflict that occurred in the Mindanao region began to see a bright spot. The existence of a peace agreement with the signing of the Bangsamoro Organic Law is a conflict resolution step so that the conflict does not escalate again.

Duterte, during his reign, issued the Bangsamoro Organic Law or the Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL) on 27 July 2018, as a replacement for the Bangsamoro Basic Law (BBL), which was initiated during Aquino's presidency and has yet to be ratified. As well as updating ARMM to BARMM which has the aim of expanding the autonomous region for the Bangsamoro. Duterte also carried out asymmetrical decentralization which served to reduce elite power and to end the insurgency in the Southern Philippines (Khaerina, 2017). He also continued the policy of the Benigno administration in the economic field in which he sought to convince investors both from within and outside the country for the overall economic development of the Philippines. This is in line with one of Rodrigo's visions which seeks to increase the economic growth of the Philippines, especially economic growth in the Mindanao region, because Mindanao actually has a wealth of natural resources in the form of minerals, so that half of the resources are managed by the government and the autonomous region of Muslim Mindanao. This is one of Rodrigo's strategies to maintain state resources so that the results can be maximized and also to gain the confidence of the separatist groups in Mindanao to stop the rebellion.

Then during the Duterte administration, he was one of the presidents of the Philippines who was serious about making peace, and actually ending the conflict in Mindanao. Moreover, he has an emotional bond with this region because it is his homeland. Back when he was campaigning, Duterte has often promised to conclude a peace agreement related to the Bangsamoro's autonomy rights. With his past on hold, Duterte understands very well the socio-cultural conditions of Muslim Mindanao, so he is able to take the right approach to end this protracted conflict and try to build a positive peace.

3.2 President Duterte's Mediation Efforts

In 2017, the island of Mindanao was hit by a crisis, this became a challenge for Duterte, who had only served one year as president, to resolve the issue of peace on his home island (Heydarian, 2017). Under Duterte's command, the Philippine government is trying to liberate Marawi City, which has been under siege for almost a month by fighters affiliated with the Islamic State (ISIS) and led by the Maute Group, a Filipino jihadist organization. This is actually a continuation of the Mamasapano tragedy during the previous administration which later caused the delay in the passage of the Bangsamoro Constitution to create new political autonomy for the Muslim population. To overcome this problem, Duterte then continued the peace process and waited for the decision of the Philippine Congress, this was certainly Duterte's attempt to create a transitional mechanism that would condition the autonomy of the Bangsamoro.

Talks about peace with the Bangsamoro were carried out by carrying out development and agrarian reform in the Mindanao region, which had previously been delayed due to the Battle of Marawi. The reform was carried out because Duterte saw that the autonomy of the Bangsamoro under the ARMM had not been maximized in the welfare of Muslims (Magdalena, 2018). The poverty rate is still high if you look at how the Bangsamoro economy is still at the lowest level compared to other communities in the Philippines. In addition, the ongoing conflicts and relentless crime have made the Mindanao region even more lagging behind in terms of development. Therefore, President Duterte is seeking long-term reforms by granting the Bangsamoro greater political autonomy in Mindanao. However, this effort faces several obstacles because the conflict in the Mindanao area is a complex conflict and has been going on for a long time. The conflict with Bangsamoro involves many separatist groups and is dynamic in nature, coupled with the different understandings of the MNLF and MILF as the main separatist groups in Mindanao, which is still a challenge that needs to be resolved.

After successfully bridging the dispute between the MNLF and MILF, on 10 and 11 July 2017 it was decided that the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) would be a mediator in bridging a peace agreement between the Philippine Government and the Bangsamoro, which was then held in Abidjan, Ivory Coast. The OIC delegated its Secretary General to hold the 4th session of the Bangsamoro Coordination Forum (BCF) on 11 July 2017 (Sandria, 2018).

In addition, the OIC's Council of Foreign Ministers suggested discussing the Tripoli Agreement 1976 Final Peace Agreement 1996 Bangsamoro Comprehensive Agreement so that the Bangsamoro could benefit from the peace talks and create a positive pattern in building relations between the Philippine government and the Bangsamoro. This was done by the OIC so that the Muslim minority in the Southern Philippines region could get their rights. In addition to discussing the resolution of the conflict in Marawi, this meeting also discussed the contents of the new Bangsamoro Constitution, in particular how to approach the

remaining issues, namely territorial issues, referendums and mineral distribution which had not previously been discussed and are still a polemic between the Philippine government and the Bangsamoro. Almost a year later, on July 6, 2018, Rodrigo Duterte gave a new law for the Mindanao region which contained the granting of wider autonomy rights to the Muslim-majority area with the aim of ending the conflict with the Philippine Government (Yasinta, 2018).

As a result, this special autonomous region is entitled to collect 75 percent of local taxes and receive 5 percent of the annual budget allocation from national income (Idrus, 2019). In addition, Rodrigo gave the Mindanao region the right to form its own parliament and courts based on Islamic values, so that they could later be used in dealing with various cases involving Muslims. The Bangsamoro Law, previously known as the Bangsamoro Basic Law (BBL) underwent a name adjustment during the Duterte administration to the Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL) and was signed by President Duterte on July 26 2018. The signing of the BOL is one of the efforts to implement a comprehensive agreement on Bangsamoro as known as Comprehensive Agreement on the Bangsamoro (CAB) as a result of peace negotiations between the MILF and the Government of the Philippines which was previously ratified in 2014.

This Organic Law is intended to replace the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) with the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region which later expanding the scope of the Bangsamoro autonomy. In addition, the BOL also expands the scope of Islamic sharia law in the Mindanao region and provides arrangements to increase regional fiscal autonomy. Basically, the Philippine government has made peace efforts by granting an autonomous region to the Bangsamoro during the administration of President Benigno Aquino III. However, the agreement was deemed a failure, therefore, Duterte continued efforts to reconcile the conflict with the Bangsamoro by establishing a BOL policy as a replacement for the BBL and updating the ARMM policy by changing it to the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) with the aim of giving full rights to the Bangsamoro. in managing their own household and expanding the Bangsamoro autonomous region (Harsono, 2018).

3.3 President Duterte's Conflict Reconciliation Against the Bangsamoro

3.3.1 Non-violent Approach

President Rodrigo Duterte is building peace with a non-violent approach to avoid further conflict. This is based on the reason that Duterte himself comes from Mindanao, so that he has a historical-psychological closeness and has known many intricacies about the existing problems, so that he was able to develop a strategy to resolve the conflict between the Bangsamoro and the Philippine Government peacefully and emphasize a peaceful approach (soft approach). President Duterte is trying to continue to carry out peace negotiations with the Bangsamoro which then involves various parties from the international world, both countries and organizations as neutral parties who are expected to be able to become mediators in resolving the Bangsamoro conflict.

This non-violence approach is as described above how the Duterte process seeks harmony between the two major groups, namely the MNLF and the MILF. So that the group later sided with the Philippine government and assisted Rodrigo in accelerating the passage of the Bangsamoro Act by the Philippine Congress. Furthermore, it is evident from this approach that a peace agreement between the Philippine government and separatist groups in Mindanao can be held mediated by the OIC. Then to complete the legality of the BOL, in 2019 President Duterte held a referendum on the autonomy of the Bangsamoro. The voting for the referendum was held in the period 21-25 January 2019 (Hasan, 2019). The results obtained are that the Philippine Electoral Commission officially announced a referendum which stated that as many as 85% of voters agreed to the establishment of an autonomous region. This makes the inauguration of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) replacing the ARMM autonomous region and makes it a historic day for Bangsamoro. It did not stop there, other efforts were made to maximize the peace process, President Duterte then formed the Bangsamoro Transition Authority (BTA) or the Bangsamoro Transition Authority on March 29, 2019 by appointing Al Haj Murad Ebrahim as the main minister.

Bangsamoro Transition Authority (BTA) is the governing body for the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Mindanao which has a working period of up to 30 June 2022, based on the BOL. With this step, Duterte hopes to improve the welfare of the Bangsamoro so that it can slowly reduce the escalation of the

conflict and build positive peace. The establishment of BTA was welcomed by Bangsamoro because the demands that had been submitted to the Philippine government were finally granted. The inauguration of the BOL and the establishment of BTA can be likened to giving the Bangsamoro independence to be able to run a government based on Islamic law which is the belief of the Bangsamoro.

Then in 2021 ago, a year before the end of BTA in 2022, which also coincided with the ouster of President Rodrigo Duterte from his reign, Hundreds of thousands of Filipino Muslims carried out a peace convoy asking Duterte to extend the BTA service period until 2025. Rodrigo also agreed. this proposal and obtained the support of Cabinet members, the president of the Philippine senate, and the chairman of Congress, resulting in the decision to extend the term of BTA until 2025 (Anadolu-Agency, 2021). This shows the success of President Rodrigo Duterte in resolving the conflict in the Southern Philippines, and his efforts to build positive peace in the region.

3.3.2 Violent Approach

It is undeniable that in the process of building peace in the Mindanao region, President Duterte experienced various obstacles, such as the Battle of Marawi which lasted for five months in 2017. This battle was an armed conflict between the Philippine government and terrorists from ISIS network groups, such as the Maute Group and Abu Sayyaf Group, which made Marawi City a stronghold for their group in Southeast Asia. At that time this battle had an impact on delaying the promulgation of the Bangsamoro Law.

Apart from these two groups, there are also separatist groups in Mindanao that have expressed support for ISIS, namely the Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighters (BIFF), led by Ismael Abu Bakar and also other separatist groups who are trying to unite to cooperate in an effort to create opportunities for ISIS to start. Establishing its new power in the Philippines. Furthermore, the separatist group wants to establish an Islamic State province in the south of the Philippines as a representation of an Islamic caliphate in Southeast Asia.

To immediately address this issue, President Duterte imposed a martial law policy to immediately arrest Hapilon, who is the leader of the Islamic State of the Philippines. The imposition of martial law then put Mindanao under the control of the Armed Forces of the Philippines (AFP) with the aim of expelling ISIS and preventing the group from controlling Philippine territory. Duterte said the implementation of the Martial Law Act in the Mindanao region, especially the Marawi region, was carried out strictly and harshly (Apriani, 2018). This is to give fear to the people of the Mindanao region who support the ISIS group. Duterte's warning was also deliberately made so that the Mindanao people remember how in its history the martial law was enforced when the reign of Ferdinand E. Marcos tended to be authoritarian, where the police and soldiers would torture, kidnap, and even kill people who were critical of the dictatorship of Ferdinand E. Marcos.

Basically, the violent approach taken by President Rodrigo Duterte is the last option because of the urgent situation and also influenced by other parties, especially the ISIS group which is trying to establish an Islamic state in the southern Philippines, which indirectly interferes with Duterte's efforts to continue negotiations peace with the Bangsamoro. So then the battle against the ISIS group became a challenge for Duterte to secure Mindanao and keep separatist groups in Mindanao to continue to cooperate with Rodrigo Duterte's government, namely resolving the prolonged conflict between the Philippine government and Bangsamoro, and formulating laws as expected.

The biggest challenge faced by the peace process in the Southern Philippines is the large number of parties involved directly or indirectly. Various groups have their own opinions and interpretations that are sometimes not in harmony with others. This makes the peace process difficult. Therefore, it is important for the Government to pay attention to various aspects, ranging from historical, political, religious, cultural, geographical, sociological, psychological aspects and social economic welfare. The government should be able to embrace various actors and opinions from various circles and form positive synergy in order to achieve positive peace in the Southern Philippines.

From the description above, it can be said that currently the Southern Philippines is still in a state of negative peace, where there are still several approaches taken by the government, both by means of soft power and hard power. However, as time goes by, it is hoped that Mindanao and Bangsamoro will soon lead to positive peace if the strategic leadership relay to the next President goes well. For this reason, President Rodrigo Duterte

placed his son, Sara Duterte, as the vice president of Bongbong Marcos Junior for achieving positive peace in the Southern Philippines in the future.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conflict in the Mindanao region has a long history for the Philippines itself. During the reign of President Duterte for the 2016-2022 period, we can see that there was a significant effort to enact the Bangsamoro Law/ Bangsamoro Organic Law (BOL), which had previously failed to materialize. The SAT analysis shows that the root of the Conflict in the Southern Philippines is the history of the Bangsamoro which since the colonial era never agreed to join the Philippine Government, besides that there are cultural and religious differences between the people of the Northern Philippines and the Southern Philippines. The accelerator of what can be seen in this conflict is the discrimination against the Bangsamoro and the Philippine government's policy that is not in favor of the Bangsamoro people which have caused economic conditions in the Southern Philippines to worsen. Finally, the trigger of this conflict is the Jabidah Tragedy which killed many Moro Muslims, the formation of the MNLF as a form of resistance to the Philippine Government, and the Martial Law policy issued by President Marcos.

The steps taken by Duterte are right, hopefully President Ferdinand Marcos Jr. can continue this good step and maintain the stability that has been built in the Southern Philippines region. Then there is a need for supervision regarding the possible return of the ISIS network separatist group, because this group can disrupt the peace that has been built between the Philippine government and the Bangsamoro. Hopefully the Marcos Jr government can emulate the approach taken by Duterte by continuing his policy so that the Bangsamoro people feel embraced as a unified part of the Philippines through religious freedom. In the SAT analysis, special attention needs to be paid to the root actors of the conflict and their accelerators, namely minority populations with different cultures and religions. In addition, it is necessary to change discriminatory attitudes towards the Moro people as well as improve welfare and the economy in the southern Philippines.

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